

ONLINE FOOD ORDERING MOBILE APPLICATION

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Background

Organization and Business Domain

LavaJava is a restaurant started by Mr. Bathiya Gunasekara and Mr. Danushka Nilanga as a partnership in 2020. This is located near Wayamba University in Kuliypitiya; at the beginning, their target market was Wayamba University, and they introduced various budget packs to the University students. Due to increasing popularity, they had to expand their target market, and now they provide service to the Kuliypitiya area.

Overview of the Existing System

Due to the second wave of the Covid-19 pandemic, the people in the Kuliypitiya area were severely affected and had to be isolated for several weeks. Because of that, they had to close the restaurant for a while, adhering to the orders of the local health officials.

Currently, they are doing all their processes manually. Given the current situation, their customer base has dwindled, and it has been extremely difficult for them to run their business.

Problems with Existing System

Still, they do not have an online food delivery system for their restaurant. In the existing system, customers have to come to the restaurant to place their orders. Customers lack visual confirmation of the food items when placing an order over the phone. They need certain employees to take the orders over the phone. And also, they are displaying food items and their prices on a board. But when prices keep on changing and new food items are being introduced, it is difficult to change those things on the board from

time to time. Therefore, this system will help the restaurant to do their business smoothly by minimizing those difficulties.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

In present operations, the customers should come to the restaurant to buy food. But due to the Covid-19 pandemic, they had to close their restaurant. Therefore, their business completely collapsed because they could not provide their services to customers, and as a startup business, they had to face many difficulties.

During the isolation period of the Kuliypitiya area, they have received a large number of orders over their hotline. But they have not been able to manage those orders due to shortcomings in the existing system. Furthermore, in those days, consumers were reluctant to eat outdoors and in public places, and that fact has had a huge impact on their business.

Requirement Analysis

Following objectives were defined for the system.

- To develop an online food ordering system that allows the customers to order food items without visiting the restaurant.
- To develop an online food ordering system that allows customers to customize their orders.
- To develop an online food ordering system that allows customers to give real-time feedback about the food and services.
- To develop an online food ordering system that will notify the confirmation of the customized orders.

There are two actors in this mobile application.

1. Admin – Primary Business Actor (LavaJava that manages customers, orders and feedback)
2. Customer – Primary Business Actor (An individual who is going to register as a customer or has registered as a customer.

All the functions have been separated into modules as follows (**Figure 1**).

- User Management Module
- Order Management Module

- Feedback Management Module

Figure 1: High-level system architecture diagram

The main functions this system will serve are as follows.

- Admin can manage users, manage menu, check orders, manage feedback, check order history, check feedback history, and filter the orders and feedback history. And also, order and feedback reports can be generated daily.
- A customer can sign up, log in or skip from the registration to the entire dashboard, change account details, view the menu, place the orders and add to the cart, navigate between menus and add items to the cart, customize orders, cancel the order, check order history, send feedback. And also, this system provides a special feature where the customer can receive the notification message automatically from the system once they have confirmed the customized order that the customer has requested.

System Development

Dart programming language is used to develop the online food ordering mobile application with the help of Android Studio. Android SDK helps developers to create mobile applications for Android Operating System.

And also, we have used Android Virtual Devices to test the app. For the backend, Firebase is used.

Conclusion

This system is built in order to solve the issues of the existing system. There was no online methodology to take orders from customers in the existing system. All the processes were done manually. This system allows customers to place orders using a graphical interface. Therefore, this system is more convenient for the customers since all the operations are done by using their mobile devices. For future enhancement, it's better to incorporate an online payment method for this application.

References

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